

Valorization of production techniques and marketing strategies for edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon

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DOI : <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4699453>

Abstract

The objective of the study is to describe the factors that stimulate the vulgarization of production techniques and marketing strategies for edible mushrooms (*pleurotus*) in Cameroon. Primary and secondary data obtained from interviewed in the Centre, Littoral, West and North-west Regions of Cameroon, typed in Microsoft word 2010 and Microsoft excel 2010 software, analysed and interpreted, using descriptive statistics. It results from the data obtained from the interviewed that, the favourable climatic conditions, the potential for access to quality and quantity inputs of production at a lower cost, the significant potential of skilled labour and the potential market for products and by-products, are the factors that promote the increase in the level of production and consumption of edible mushrooms (*pleurotus*) in Cameroon. It also results from this study that, the cultivation of edible mushrooms (*pleurotus*) is a source of job creation for the vulnerable population as well as a source of enhancement of the agro-pastoral crops in Cameroon. Likewise, the cultivation of edible oyster mushrooms could help to reduce significantly the impact of environmental degradation, and could help improve the economic growth of the agro-food sub-sector. Results obtained from data analysis showed that,

between 2017 and 2018, despite the difficulties related to quality and quantity access to inputs at lower cost, the edible mushroom sub-sector in the study area achieved a job growth rate of 16.6%. 44% of mushrooms producer's interviewees confirm that they were satisfied for their activities related to seed multiplication and the production of edible oyster mushrooms. According to the interviewees, the link in the value of mushrooms production requires more investment. Between 2017 and 2019, the network members of CoopSDEM COOP-CA achieved an increase in their average investment, for the collect of dry corn cobs, for the multiplication of seeds and for production of oyster mushrooms of 15%, 8% and 6,7%, respectively. It emerges from the results of the data analysis that, for the same level of annual production (600 kg) of oyster mushrooms, sold at the same price per kg, the mushrooms grower of Bafoussam achieves a result 1.8 times more and 12.2 times more than the mushrooms grower at Yaoundé and Douala, respectively. The turnover from which the mushrooms grower of Yaoundé does not realize any loss or gain is 1 016 667 CFA F (1 552 euro) for this level of production. Consequently, the return on investment of the producer of Bafoussam is faster than that of Yaoundé and Douala.

Keywords : Valorization, Mushroom, Production techniques, Marketing Strategies

Résumé

L'objectif de cette étude est de décrire les facteurs qui stimulent la vulgarisation des techniques de production et des stratégies de commercialisation des champignons comestibles *pleurotus* au Cameroun. Les données primaires et secondaires obtenues auprès des enquêtés dans les régions du Centre, du Littoral, de l'Ouest et du Nord-ouest du Cameroun, saisies dans les logiciels Microsoft word 2010 et Microsoft excel 2010, ont été analysées et interprétées, au moyen de la statistique descriptive. Il ressort des données

obtenues auprès des enquêtés que, les conditions climatiques favorables, le potentiel important d'accès aux intrants de production de qualités et en quantité, à moindre coût, le potentiel important de main d'œuvre qualifié et le potentiel important de marché de consommation des produits et sous-produits, sont les facteurs qui favorisent l'augmentation du niveau de production et de consommation des champignons comestibles *pleurotus* au Cameroun. Il ressort également de cette étude que, la culture des champignons comestibles

pleurotus est une source de création d'emplois pour les populations vulnérables et une source de valorisation des autres spéculations agropastorales au Cameroun. De même, la culture des champignons comestibles pleurotus pourrait contribuer à réduire significativement l'impact de la dégradation de l'environnement et pourrait contribuer à améliorer la croissance économique du sous-secteur agroalimentaire. Les résultats de l'analyse des données montrent que, entre 2017 et 2018, malgré les difficultés liées à l'accès aux intrants de qualité et en quantité, à moindre coût, le sous-secteur champignons comestibles dans la zone d'étude a réalisé un taux d'accroissement des emplois de 16,6%. Des myciculteurs enquêtés, 44% affirme être satisfait des gains de productions réalisés, liées à la production des champignons comestibles pleurotus et à la multiplication de ses semences. Entre 2017 et 2019, les

membres du réseau de la CoopSDEM COOP-CA ont réalisés un taux d'accroissement de leurs investissements pour la collecte des rafles sèche de maïs, pour la multiplication des semences et pour la production des carpophores, de 15%, 8% et 6,7%, respectivement. Il ressort des résultats de l'analyse des données que, pour le même niveau de production (600 kg) annuel de carpophores pleurotus, vendu au même prix le kilogramme, le myciculteur de Bafoussam réalise un résultat net 1,8 fois plus et 12,2 fois plus que le myciculteur de Yaoundé et de Douala, respectivement. Le chiffre d'affaire à partir duquel le myciculteur de Yaoundé ne réalise ni perte, ni gain (seuil de rentabilité) est de 1 016 667 franc CFA (1 552 euro) pour ce niveau de production. Par conséquent, le retour sur investissement du producteur de Bafoussam est plus rapide que celui de Yaoundé et de Douala.

Mots-Clés : Valorisation, Champignons, Technique de production, Stratégies marketing

1. Introduction

In most developing countries of Africa in general and in Cameroon in particular, the increase in the population of young cities is due to series of factors, among which, the internal migration of vulnerable individuals located in rural areas, who wish to meet the challenges of having better living conditions (Manirakiza, 2012). This increase of the urban population is not accompanied by an increase of agro-pastoral production and a diversification of manufactured products from local agro-industries (MINADER-DESA, 2012). The phenomenon of the endogenous growth of the young urban population also results from the problem of under employment, which limits their purchasing power and this at a cost to their daily well-being. According to Ninkwango (2014), the promotion of the cultivation, gathering and marketing of edible mushrooms is a possible solution to this great scourge, linked to the rural exodus of young people in Cameroon. Based on observation, since 2015, Cooperative Society with Board of Director for Sustainable Development of Edible Mushrooms (CoopSDEM COOP-CA), with the support of its technical and financial partners, has significantly contributed to promoting youth entrepreneurship in Cameroon, through gathering, cultivation, transformation and distribution of edible fungi (Djomene et al., 2019). Indeed, favourable climatic conditions, existence of a significant potential for access to inputs of better quality and in sufficient quantity at lower cost, existence of qualified labour and existence of a real and potential market for the consumption of products and by-products, are the factors that promote the increase

of national production of edible oyster mushrooms (*pleurotus*). According to Ministry of Economy, Planning and Regional Development (MINEPAT) (2010), several factors favour the improvement of the living conditions of populations in Cameroon, including the cultivation of edible mushrooms. The technical production itinerary can be accessible to all social categories (intellectual or not young people, elderly, disabled, etc.) on one hand. and on the other hand, the farm exploitation cost is not expensive because certain raw material and equipment available locally at lower cost. This study consist on one hand to present the factors that leads to increase the national production of edible mushrooms (*pleurotus*) in Cameroon, and on the other hand, the factors that favour the improvement of the living conditions of the vulnerable population through the cultivation and commercialisation of edible mushrooms.

2. Materiel and Methods

2.1. Material

The material used for this study is of various kinds and uses. Samples of dried edible mushrooms (*pleurotus*) were used in the laboratory to test the quality of the products. Microsoft Word 2010 and Microsoft Excel 2010 software were used for data entry and processing, for analysis and interpretation of the data collected. Samples of substrates such as: dry corn cobs, sawdust and Sissongo, were used to assess the yield's rate of the production, depending on the nature of the substrate in a given locality. The hydrometer and thermometer were used to measure the humidity and temperature of

substrate in the incubation and fructification rooms of the production house.

2.2. Method

2.2.1. Factors that stimulate the increase of the level of national production of mushrooms (pleurotus) in Cameroon

2.2.1.1. Favourable climatic conditions to obtain a good production yield

The production of edible mushrooms (pleurotus) is more profitable in localities with a humid tropical climate. In Cameroon, the western, north western and Central Regions are made up of localities with high production yields, due to favourable climates parameters (temperature, humidity and air), mainly in localities where human activity is recorded as little as possible (Djomene et al., 2019). In the western and north western Regions, the lowest average temperatures are around 10.2°C to 16°C. The optimal temperatures do not go beyond 25°C (Djomene et al., 2020). The same temperature parameters exist in certain localities in the Centre Region (INS, 2015). The yield rates for the production of edible mushrooms in the favourable zone are 33% to 65% after a production cycle. The average humidity level recorded in the study area is 78%. The oyster mushrooms producers on the Littoral Region and part of the Southwest Region obtain good production yields, because of the constant humidity rate (85%) which prevails. Nevertheless, the regions of South, East and Adamaoua are not left out, for obtaining good production yields of oyster mushrooms.

2.2.1.2. High potential for access production inputs at lower cost

Access to production factors of quality and in quantity at a lower cost is still a major constraint in agriculture in Cameroon, for all the different groups: seeds and plants phytosanitary product, fertilizers, treatment equipment and devices (MINADER-DRCQ, 2016). Among the many advantages of cultivating edible

oyster mushrooms and multiplication of its seeds in Cameroon, we note their ability to recycle agricultural production residues: corn cobs, rice staw, bean tops, plantain leaves, etc., used as a production medium (Diansambu et al., 2016). Cameroon is a country with a varied ecosystem on the one hand, and population in town and on the outskirts of which the level of culture is well established on the other hand. These assets allow potential and real mushrooms growers to access to certain production inputs locally at lower cost. The cultivation of edible oyster mushrooms does not require the use of fertilizers and pesticides, in Regions with high production yields, such as the Northwest, the West and part of the Centre and the Littoral (Ninkwango, 2014). MINADER's interventions through Support Program of the Development of the Edible Mushroom Subsector (PADFC) and Direction of Regulation of Quality Control of Agricultural products (DRCQ) make it possible to increase the supply sites for certified (white) seeds of edible oyster mushrooms at a lower cost, in the various production areas of the country.

2.2.1.3. Technical itinerary for the production of edible oyster mushrooms

According to Ninkwango (2007), anyone can cultivate edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon, because the acquisition of technology is easy and suitable for each individual, regardless of their culture and social status. In Cameroon, young people graduated or not, retire or representatives of Professional Agro-pastoral Organization (PAO) are increasingly entering the edible mushrooms sub-sector in Cameroon, with the support of MINADER-PADFC (Djomene et al., 2016). This MINADER program organizes and holds group training in production mushrooms each year in the departmental and regional delegation of Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER), with the aim of increasing the level of labour qualified the sub-sector. More and more, local elites and economics operators practice the cultivation of edible oyster mushrooms

Board 1 : (a) Academic internship ; (b) Retraining seminar for MINADER-DRCQ and (c) Training as part of trip to study

Board 2 : (a) Sales of wild mushrooms in the market ; (b) Sales of fresh pleurotus in a super market; (c) Group sales of small producers; (d) Pudine of mushroom in a restaurant

through intermediaries, to support local development effort on the one hand and on the other hand to diversify their income. Board 1 illustrates the end of the academic internship for students from Higher Institute of Agriculture and Management of Obala (ISAGO) and Faculty of Agronomy and Agricultural Sciences (FASA) of University of Dschang; a retraining seminar for MINADER-DRCQ executives at CoopSDEM COOP-CA and training as part of trip to study of student from the University of Yaoundé 1 at PADFC, respectively.

2.2.1.4. Existence of a potential market for consumption of products in Cameroon

The market for the commercialisation of edible mushrooms in Cameroon is in a situation of pure and perfect competition, characterized by: the atomicity of supply and demand, the homogeneity of product and by-products, freedom of entry and exit to the market, perfect information for market actors and perfect mobility of production factors (CoopSDEM COOP-CA, 2019). According to MINEPAT (2010), in 2004, Cameroon imported 82 tons of edible table mushrooms, for a monetary value of 123 million CFA F (187,137 euros). In 2018, the importation of edible table mushrooms is estimated at 250 tons, for a monetary value of 500 million CFA F (763,359 euros), or 3 times more than in 2004. The national demand of edible mushrooms produced in Cameroon, experienced a growth rate of 4.6% between 2010 and 2014. Households, restaurants and hotels managers, and supermarket department managers represents 47.5%, 24.5% and 20.9% of the demand for mushrooms in Cameroon in 2019, respectively. An interview conducted by CoopSDEM COOP-CA, with the support of MINADER-PADFC at the end of 2018, estimated the national consumption needs of edible mushrooms in 2019 at 500 tons, with more than 70% of applicants (foreigner's residents and tourists and well-off nationals) located in the country's major urban centers. There is high demand for production and residues of edible oyster mushrooms

in Cameroon, expressed by agro-pastoral farmers, restaurants and industries. Board 2 illustrates the distribution segments of edible oyster mushrooms from Cameroon production.

2.2.2. Improvement of living standard of the population trough mushrooms cultivation

2.2.2.1. Creation of new job opportunities for the local population

The empowerment of decentralized territorial communities in Cameroon is a way for local development actors to contribute to significantly and sustainably improve their living conditions, through the development of agro-pastoral activities in general and the popularization of production techniques of edible mushrooms in particular. The edible mushroom sub-sector offers many job opportunities to the local population (youths and women) exposed to poverty (MINEPAT, 2010). Population without employment have the possibility of assuring the collection, grinding and conditioning of the raw material for the production of edible oyster mushrooms. Unemployed population themselves, have the opportunity to ensuring the recycling of cakes mycelium residue to supply the breeders with food and litter (fowls, pigs, fish, etc.) on the one hand, and on the another hand, to supply the farmers with compost (MINADER-PADFC, 2017). Craftsmen have the opportunity of producing materials and equipment's related in the production of edible oyster mushrooms. They consist materials and equipment's used in pasteurisation (mechanised barrels), dryers for the transformation of fresh mushrooms, inoculation box for seeds multiplication and shelves for the disposition of packs of substrates and mycelium cakes in the incubation and fructification unit, respectively. Farmers have the opportunity of supplying to mushrooms producers primary materials like corn cobs, Palme cone residues, bean tops, etc. (CoopSDEM COOP-CA, 2019). Board 3 illustrate the craft products for the production of edible oyster mushrooms and its seeds.

Board 3 : (a) Cultivation shelters built in straw; (b) Corn cobs crushing; (c) Home-made pasteurizer; (d) Handcrafted electric gas dryer with fan

Board 4 : (a) Mycelium cake residue ; (b) Corn cobs substrates; (c) Maize grain substrates; (d) Sissongo substrates

2.2.2.2. Promotion of other agro-pastoral crops through mushroom cultivation

The production of edible stem mushrooms in general and edible oyster mushrooms in particular, requires the used of agricultural production products and residues such as: grains of corn cobs, potatoes, bean tops, etc. The above product and by-products serve as raw material or production support for edible oyster mushrooms and its seeds (Ninkwango, 2007). Agricultural production residues recycled for mushrooms cultivation, allows small farmers to limit their production cost of oyster mushrooms (*pleurotus specie*) and to diversify their income (Djomene et al., 2019). The big corn growers and wood processor, recycle production residues to supply the big mushrooms producers with corn cobs and sawdust/wood chips, for fees. In the intensive livestock sub-subtor, production residues of edible oyster mushrooms (waste mycelium cakes) are recycled to serve as feed and bedding for animals (chickens, pigs, goats, oxen, fish, etc.); these waste recycled mycelium cakes are also used by agricultural producers for soil amendment, which improves agro-pastoral production (Ninkwango, 2007). Board 4 illustrates the products and residues of agricultural production being promoted in the cultivation of mushrooms in Cameroon.

2.2.2.3. Decrease of the impact of environmental degradation through myciculture

In addition to recycling nutrients and helping plants

and crops to grow efficiently, fungi provide us with compounds that produce antibiotics, statins, etc., to treat certain cancers, cholesterol, hypertension and immune suppressors (Marine, 2015). Some fungi (endophytes and mycorrhiza) can help plants cope with significant stresses, such as increased temperature and drought. Advances in the agricultural application could translate into improved food security, environmental sustainability and increased income from agricultural production (ONF, 2019). The production of edible oyster mushrooms is above-ground and under-shelter, which does not require the occupation of very large areas of land and which consequently, limits the destruction of the ecosystems of our environment (Nninkwango, 2013). According to Christian et al. (1996), the rot fungi (saprotrophs and mycorrhizal) of wood and litter are a great enzymatic richness, producing both unspecific, exo-cellular systems and with strong oxidizing power (in particular the ligninolytic system) and intracellular systems involved in the transformation of xenobiotics. This enzymatic richness allows these fungi to carry out a large number of chemical reactions (oxidation, reduction, hydrolysis and synthesis) on xenobiotics polluting various chemical structures (polarity, lipophilic, etc.) (Christian et al., 1996). The white rot of litter and humus thus a fundamental role in the recycling of plant waste and debris (Pierre et al., 2010).

2.2.2.4. Contribution of the edible mushrooms sub-sector to the economic growth of Cameroon

Edible mushrooms are among the food products

with high potential for creating added value. This characteristic makes the edible mushrooms sub-sector, one of the sector to prioritized by the cameroonian public authorities, to help raise the growth rate of the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the agro-food sub-sector (Djomene et al., 2019). Population in town and in the country side are increasingly interested in the production of edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon. The consequence is an increase in the employment rate in the agro-food subsector. Another consequence of the production of edible oyster mushrooms is that, to providing well-being to actors in the mushrooms sub-sector, because it contributes to reducing poverty and also contributes to improving health and environmental education for local population (CoopSDEM COOP-CA, 2019). Another consequence of mushrooms production is that, it improves the health of vulnerable population. In fact the confirmation of edible oyster mushrooms has antiviral, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-hyper cholesterolic, anti-cancer and immune modulating effects. The wealth generated

by production mushrooms is distributed equitably, in proportion to the contribution of each actor in the mushrooms sub-sector (PADFC, 2018).

3. Results

3.1. Price evolution of consumables for the production of edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon

Figure 1 illustrates the price evolution of consumables for the production of edible mushrooms (*pleurotus*) in the study area between 2015 and 2019.

3.2. Conditions for obtaining consumables for the production of edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon

Figure 2 illustrates the percentage of the conditions for obtaining the consumables, for the production of edible oyster mushrooms.

3.3. Net job creation in the Cameroonian-produced edible mushrooms sub-sector

Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of job creation in the cameroonian production of edible mushrooms sub-sector, according to the interviewees.

Figure 1: Price evolution of consumables for the production of pleurotus between 2015 and 2019

Figure 2 : Percentage of the conditions for obtaining consumables for the production pleurotus

Figure 3: Change in net job creation in percentage in the Cameroonian-produced edible mushrooms sub-sector

3.4. Profit made by inputs suppliers and oyster mushrooms growers in Cameroon

Figure 4 illustrates the evolution of benefits obtained by interviewees through the distribution of production inputs and edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon.

3.5. Evolution of investments related to the production and marketing of edible oyster mushrooms sub-sector in Cameroon

Figure 5 illustrates the evolution of the investments

made for each activity of the edible mushrooms sub-sector, according to the interviewees.

3.6. Calculation of break-even point and dead point for each producer of edible oyster mushrooms

3.6.1. Reclassification of charges for the production of edible oyster mushrooms, according to the study area

The data collected made it possible to assess all the loads (variable and fixed) for a production capacity of 600 kg of edible fresh oyster mushrooms, per year in

Figure 4 : Evolution of the profits obtained by the inputs suppliers and by the mushrooms producers interviewees

Figure 5: Level of investments made for each activity of the edible mushrooms sub-sector, according to the interviewees

Table 1: Reclassification of annual charges for the production of 600 kg of edible fresh oyster mushrooms, depending on the study area

Factors of production	Ydé town (CFAF)		Douala town (CFAF)		Bafoussam town (CFAF)	
	Variable C.	Fixed C.	Variable C.	Fixed C.	Variable C.	Fixed C.
Dry corn cobs	111 000	-	129 000	-	87 000	-
Procurement costs	30 000	-	35 000	-	25 000	-
Certified seeds	320 400	-	438 200	-	187 200	-
Banko plus	10 000	-	10 000	-	10 000	-
Urea	1 500	-	1 000	-	1 000	-
Slaked lime	11 000	-	10 500	-	9 000	-
Plastic bags	15 000	-	18 000	-	14 400	-
Firewood	30 000	-	38 400	-	24 000	-
Wages	100 000	300 000	125 000	300 000	100 000	300 000
Water and electricity	-	25 000	-	30 000	-	20 000
Dues and taxes	19 982	50 000	19 784	50 000	29 618	50 000
Amortization grants	-	174 000	-	174 000	-	174 000
Total 1	648 882	549 000	824 884	554 000	487 218	544 000
TOTAL 2	1 197 882		1 378 884		1 031 218	

Table 2: Table of fixed assets and depreciation at 31/12/2020, for a production capacity of mushrooms producer's interviewees, of 1,200 kg of pasteurized substrate per production cycle

Element	purchase value	Duration (year)	Previous depreciation	depreciation of the year	Cumulative depreciation	Net book value
01 plot of 100 m ²	700 000	100	28 000	7 000	35 000	665 000
01 mushrooms house	2 000 000	20	400 000	100 000	500 000	1 500 000
04 Rows of shelves	200 000	10	80 000	20 000	100 000	100 000
03 SPN (barrel of 200L)	150 000	05	120 000	30 000	150 000	-
02 Watering can	10 000	03	10 000	-	10 000	-
02 40 liter basins	8 000	03	8 000	-	8 000	-
01 Wheelbarrow	30 000	05	24 000	6 000	30 000	-
01 Backpack sprayer	35 000	05	28 000	7 000	35 000	-
01 Sensible scale	20 000	05	16 000	4 000	20 000	-
02 Bucket of 10L	3 000	02	3 000	-	3 000	-
TOTAL	3 156 000		717 000	174 000	891 000	2 265 000

Table 3: Differential operating account of edible mushrooms growers interviewed in the study area

Eléments	Yaoundé fungus growers		Douala fungus growers		Bafoussam fungus grower	
	Amount	(%)	Amount	(%)	Amount	(%)
Turnover	1 410 000	100	1 410 000	100	1 410 000	100
Variables Charges	648 882	46.02	824 884	58.5	487 218	34.6
M/VC (gross margin)	761 118	54	585 116	41.5	922 782	65.4
Fixed charges	549 000	39	554 000	39.3	544 000	38.6
Result (net margin)	212 118	15.04	31 116	2.2	378 782	26.9

three cycles, at Yaoundé in the Centre Region, in Douala (Littoral Region) and in Bafoussam (West Region) of Cameroon. The table 1 shows the reclassification of annual charges for the production of 600 kg of edible fresh oyster mushrooms, according to the study area.

3.6.2. Calculation of the fixed assets and depreciation table as at 31/12/N, according to the production capacity of the mushrooms producers interviewees

Table 2 shows in the fifth year of operation the fixed assets and depreciation on 31/12/2020, of the mushrooms producer's interviewees, with production capacity of 1,200 kg of pasteurized substrate per production cycle.

3.6.3. Calculation of break-even point and dead point of the mushrooms producers interviewed, according to the study area

The sowing rates practiced by the mushrooms growers interviewed are respectively: 12% in Yaoundé, 12% in Douala and 9% in Bafoussam. The production capacities are: 500 bundles, 580 bundles and 381 bundles for the edible mushrooms growers interviewed in Yaoundé, Douala and Bafoussam, respectively. Table 3 illustrates

the differential operating account of edible mushrooms growers interviewed in the study area for 600 kg of fresh edible oyster mushrooms produced and sold.

Table 4 shows break-even point and dead point achieved by the edible mushrooms growers interviewed in the study area, for 600 kg of edible oyster mushrooms fresh, produced and sold.

4. Discussion

It emerge from this study that, 92% of mushrooms producers interviewees on the one hand and 76% on the other hand denounce the drastic increase, from the simple to double, the price of plastic packaging for the conditioning of the substrate and the price of dry stalks of corn (raw material), respectively. The main reason is linked to the supply which is much lower than the demand. According to 63% of the mushrooms producer's interviewees, the high cost to transport is the main cause of the difficult conditions of supply of quality and quantity dry corn cobs. Thus the government intervention, through the establishment of raw material collections points, could lead to easy and low-cost

Table 4: Break-even point and dead point generated by the edible mushrooms growers interviewed in the study area

Elements	Yaoundé fungus growers	Douala fungus growers	Bafoussam fungus grower
	Value in CFAF	Value in CFAF	Value in CFAF
Turnover	1 410 000	1 410 000	1 410 000
Margin on variable cost	761 118	585 116	922 782
Margin rate on VC	0.54	0.41	0.65
Fixed charges	549 000	554 000	544 000
Break-even point	1 016 667	1 351 220	836 923
Dead point	8 months, 1 week	11 months, 5 days	7 months, 1 day

access and consequently improve the production yields of edible oyster mushrooms. According to 67.2% of interviewees, the edible mushrooms sub-sector in the study area achieved an average employment growth rate of 16.6% between 2018 and 2019. 44% of mushrooms producer's interviewees confirm that they were satisfied for their activities related to seed multiplication and the production of edible oyster mushrooms. The production gains made stem from the sense of professionalism and the technical and strategic capacities which characterize these mushrooms producers. More than 50% of mushrooms producer's interviewees still find it difficult to optimize their production yield, because of the poor technical capacities which characterize them and because of the frenzied taste for profit. According to the interviewees, the link in the value of mushrooms production requires more investment. Between 2017 and 2019, the network members of CoopSDEM COOP-CA achieved an increase in their average investment, for the collect of dry corn cobs, for the multiplication of seeds and for production of oyster mushrooms of 15%, 8% and 6.7%, respectively. The basic reason is linked to the increased demand for the production inputs of oyster mushrooms and its seeds. According to the interviewees, the amount of variable production cost change from one locality to another, because of the easy access or not of quality inputs. The cost of depreciation of goods in the fifth year of operation on the companies interviewees is 174 000 CFAF. The result of the data analysis show that, for an annual production capacity of 600 kg of fresh oyster mushrooms, the time taken to make the return on investment is different from one locality to another. Indeed, it takes 2 months 3 weeks and 4 days, and 4 months, 1 week and 4 days more for the mushrooms producer's interviewees in the city of Douala, respectively, compared to the mushroom producers of Yaoundé and Bafoussam, so that their business figure carried out results in no loss or gain.

5. Conclusion

At the end of this study, it emerges that, the climatic conditions, the high potential for access to production inputs at a lower cost, the high potential for skilled labour and the existence of a real and potential market for consumption of goods and services, are the main factors that could promote an exponential increase in the level of annual production of edible oyster mushrooms in Cameroon. It also emerges from this study that, edible mushrooms production is an indisputable means of creating new business opportunities; it could also enables small agro-pastoral farmers to improve their income. Mushrooms production could also contribute significantly on the one hand to reducing the effects of environmental degradation and on the other hand, could contribute to improving the level of agricultural gross domestic product (GDP) of Cameroon. As a ripple effect, more noticeable interventions from national and international publics and private's institutions are needed to ensure effective and efficient support for actors in the mushrooms sub-sector. The results of the study shows that, when the production of edible oyster mushrooms is ensured by individuals endowed with technical and strategic capacities who do not suffer from any dispute, the production gains are greater, compared to the production gains of its substitute and complementary products such as meats, fish's, vegetables and fruits. The result of the study also shows that, the time taken to realize the return on investment of the production edible oyster mushrooms depends on the production area, on the level of experience of the producer and on his sense of professionalism.

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